

SALES MANAGEMENT METHODS IN THE TOURISM SECTOR INDUSTRIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13898585>

Abstract. *In this article, we are analyzing the experience of the tourism industry in the application of innovative sales management methods. Particular attention is paid to innovative methods tested in the work of the largest tourism companies.*

Keywords: *sales, management, tourism, tourism activities, tourism products, innovations, innovative methods.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье анализируется опыт туристической отрасли по применению инновационных методов управления продажами. Особое внимание уделено инновационным методам, апробированным в работе крупнейших туристических компаний.*

Ключевые слова: *продажи, управление, туризм, туристическая деятельность, туристические продукты, инновации, инновационные методы.*

Annotasiya. *Ushbu maqolada biz savdoni boshqarishning innovatsion usullarini qo'llash bo'yicha turizm sanoati tajribasini tahlil qilamiz. Yirik sayyohlik kompaniyalari faoliyatida sinovdan o'tgan innovatsion usullarga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda.*

Kalit so'zlar: *sotish, menejment, turizm, turistik faoliyat, turistik mahsulotlar, innovatsiyalar, innovatsion usullar.*

Introduction

Creating an attractive tourist product is the most important way to implement the marketing strategy of a tourist company. This is directly related to the production process in a tourist company. Product policy requires the use of coordinated decisions on production and sales in relation to the volume and weight of the tourist product. The issue of forming and promoting tourist products for the tourist business is strategic, since their effectiveness depends on business decisions.

In this regard, the topic of this work seems timely and relevant.

Sales management methods. The analysis shows that the tourism industry as a whole has a number of features. This is a service and is usually quite expensive. The region also experiences clear seasonal changes, with peaks and valleys occurring every few months. This means that in order to balance and stabilize sales, it is necessary to offer customers high-margin products at reduced prices that still generate profit.

In this area, it is especially important that customer service representatives are well trained in sales techniques and have the ability to be persistent, problem-solving and negotiating.

The tourism services sales market is oversaturated with offers, its presence and uniqueness are due to fierce competition caused by the following factors:

1. Competition increases as the number of travel agencies offering similar services increases.

2. Demand decreases, competition increases. Companies are forced to compete with their customers using new marketing tactics and tricks.

3. Demand for services may change seasonally, so discounts and benefits are used to increase sales.

4. Stabilization of prices for similar services will allow customers to choose companies that offer the largest number of bonuses.

5. Change tourism products by improving the quality of services provided.

6. Monitor your competitors' sales successes and efforts.

7. Attracting “outsiders” to the market, creating new conditions and playing against the rules.

As researchers note, competitor analysis and market mapping allow travel sales professionals to increase their advantage because they identify weaknesses and become less susceptible to external changes [4]. It is also indicated that various methods of promoting tourism products and services are aimed at cooperation with different groups:

1. *Company staff.* Bonuses and incentives increase their interest in the company.

2. *Travel retailers and retail agents.* We need souvenirs with the company logo, participation in exhibitions, performances, general advertising programs with organizational or financial support.

3. *Client group.* They focus on online reviews, souvenirs, hotel travel agency tokens, as well as small rewards and items, free coupons and affordable travel financing.

4. *Joint advertising work with representatives of other business areas.* The survey results show that sales managers in tourism companies often use the following sales techniques. Promotion of tourism products increases customer loyalty and leads to brand recognition. This increases the value of tourism products in the market. The company states that the sale of services and products is carried out only in the interests of customers and not for profit.

Analysis of surveys of tourism consumers helps to identify priority criteria for choosing a travel agency [5]. The importance of this for potential tourists can be determined by the following criteria:

- price of the trip, existence of long-term employment relationship with the company charging for travel services, and reason for providing the discount;
- company reputation based on online reviews of relatives and friends;
- corporate office, location, interior design and feeling of personal communication with employees (level of qualification, knowledge, politeness on various issues affecting tourists);
- time and authority of the company to be protected in the market, availability of licenses, time policy (policies) and choice of available travel products;
- possibility of obtaining insurance from the company, its type and cost for tourists taking into account the insurance events specified in the tour purchase agreement;
- form of cooperation of the company with airlines and hotel owners (scheduled or charter flights, booking or use of office premises);
- transport and household services;
- official website of the company with a convenient system of browsing and commenting on the Internet, as well as comprehensive information about tourism and additional services provided on the website.

In this case, profit is the result of the company's efforts to satisfy the desires of tourists. By creating the appropriate environment, they carry out propaganda activities that influence the public and make tourism organizations attractive to target groups.

Various incentives provide a short-term increase in the purchase of a service or product. This is another element of promoting a tourist product. Therefore, it is not advisable to constantly stimulate sales.

All methods of promoting tourism products take into account the interests of people.

1. The discount club offers discounts on tourist purchases.
2. Hot sales at low prices.
3. Off-season promotions.
4. Revitalize the agent network by increasing commission rates, rewards and bonuses.

Conclusion

Any business that wants to operate effectively and in the long term needs effective business management. High competition forces businesses to keep up with the latest tools and technologies because of their ability to quickly solve new problems.

A competent sales organization solves a number of problems that are critical to the company's success. Thanks to the impeccable work of employees, customer loyalty increases, final sales figures increase, and employee productivity increases.

Timely analysis of the obtained results allows us to revise current and long-term plans, change methods depending on market conditions and thereby provide all the conditions for increasing the profitability of the enterprise. Thus, it should be noted that the sale of tourism products should be carefully thought out first. When selling tourism products, it is necessary to take into account all options and forms of implementation and change them depending on real conditions.

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